

THE ROLE OF AUTHENTIC VIDEO IN DEVELOPING SOCIACULTURAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract: The article highlights the history of the development of communicative competence and forming the process of sociocultural competence as a main component of communicative competence. The author describes the features of sociocultural competence and its correlation to using authentic video materials. She considers the effectiveness of the method of using authentic videos in foreign language teaching as high. The advantages and disadvantages of using such materials for educational purposes are analyzed using examples. The recommendations are given on the methodological adaptation of this material to the learning environment. At the same time, the selection criteria for authentic video materials are suggested based on theories of scientists.

Key words: Authentic material, sociocultural competence, video material, criteria, selection of video, duration
The Role Of Authentic Video In Developing Sociocultural Competence
Linguistic pedagogy has been studying the components of communicative competence for many years.

The introduction of the communicative competence construct in foreign language acquisition helps to cope with a number of problems in language teaching. It also is seen as a solution of an important task in achievement of functional abilities in the target language of learners. “Competence” was first

mentioned by Labov in 1966 as a reflection on the Chomsky’s theory of “an ideal speaker-listener” that provoked great interest of scientists to the structure of communicative competence. Canale & Swain (1980) outlined their own understanding of communicative competence according to which it includes four areas of knowledge: grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence and strategic competence. In addition, Krashen (1981) states that: “Language acquisition is very similar to the process children use in acquiring first and second languages. It requires meaningful interaction in the target language--natural communication--in which speakers are concerned not with the form of their utterances but with the messages they are conveying and understanding”. Thus, communicative competence in foreign language is seen as an ability to speak competently not only knowing the grammar structures of language, but also knowing what to say, to whom, in what circumstances and how to say the message. Communicative competence has always been viewed as a complex phenomenon, formed by two to five components according to various scientific approaches. It has been proved that sociolinguistic components play an important role in development of communicative competence. Sociolinguistic competence has been the subject of many studies (Lum 2004, Belenyuk 2008, Koester 2009) where the authors consider the process of occurrence, development and modern concept of sociolinguistic competence, clarify its essence and component composition; determine the importance for the formation of communicative competence. The following definition is proposed for the context of this paper. “This competence is a set of linguistic and non-linguistic (non-verbal) means of communication, as well as the learner’s ability to choose and use them to fit a specific communicative situation and sociocultural norms of society”.

State Educational Standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan also focuses on the sociolinguistic competence and highlights students’ ability to choose the right linguistic forms and ways of expression depending on the situation, the communicative purpose and the intentions of the speaker. Sociolinguistic competence includes sociocultural competence that provides the ability to recognize the national characteristics of the country of the language studied and

behave accordingly in the situations with native speakers. Language and culture are tightly connected with each other and obviously they cannot develop separately. Culture is the basis of communication. In teaching a foreign language, great attention should be paid to teaching intercultural communication as well as to teaching linguistic knowledge so that learners' intercultural communicative competence can be enhanced. Language learners should be introduced to language patterns but main sociolinguistic, sociocultural phenomenon should be paid specific attention. Linguistic markers of social relations: the use and choice of forms of greeting, addressing, conversation, the use and choice of exclamations, interjections, parasitic words, etc. thanks, intentional disregard for the formulas of politeness; expressions of folk wisdom: proverbs, sayings, idioms, signs, clichés, evaluative statements. Registers of communication: formal, neutral, informal. Dialect and accent (lexicon, grammar, phonology, vocal characteristics (rhythm, loudness of speech), paralinguistic, sign language) of social classes, regional and national origins, ethnic groups, groups professional activities.

Main speech communication conventions in a foreign language society; willingness to overcome the influence of stereotypes and to carry out intercultural dialogue in the general and professional areas of communication.

The classifications of linguistic markers of social relations diverge widely in different languages and cultures depending on such factors as social status, the level of closeness of human relationships, and speech styles. The forms of etiquette are also different in different countries and can become a source of inter-ethnic misunderstanding with misinterpretation.

We know that at the beginner stage of learning a foreign language obviously a neutral communication register is used. This is due to the following reasons: in communication with foreigners, native speakers use speech and hope to hear neutral vocabulary. Mastering more formal or familiar registers of communication will require more time and effort from a learner, since inaccurate or late use of this register can lead to misunderstanding. In order to avoid such kind of misunderstandings in communication with native speakers language

learners should master sociocultural knowledge about country of the language being studied.

Obviously, in order to develop sociocultural competence, a foreign language learner needs acquire certain knowledge about the lifestyle, traditions and customs of a foreign language speaker, develop the ability to choose and use adequate language forms and means depending on the purpose and situation of communication, on the social roles of communication participants. Acquisition of information about the lifestyle, traditions and customs of the people should happen in the classroom through the activities that are planned by the EL teachers. It is important to remember that social behavior in specific situations of communication in the country of the language being studied can help greatly to design such activities. An example can be authentic video materials, which are designed to prepare students for the perception of a multicultural reality and for smooth entry into it by developing sociocultural competence, learners' achievement and motivation.

It is obvious that not every plot recorded on live video can be used for teaching and learning purposes. When selecting authentic videos for their use in the development and improvement of communication competence, it is necessary to be guided by a number of criteria. Below I selected the most significant of them based on suggestions of Zhoglina.

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